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ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ОНЛАЙН-ОБУЧЕНИЯ

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CHARACTERISTICS OF ONLINE LEARNING

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Аннотация

В статье раскрываются преимущества и недостатки онлайн-обучения в образовательном процессе. Отмечено, что после распространения пандемии коронавируса она оставила свой след и в системе образования. Некоторые образовательные центры перешли на формат онлайн-обучения с традиционной формы. В статье подчеркивается, что онлайн-обучение является эффективным по времени и стоимости, чего не наблюдается на традиционных очных занятиях. Подчеркивается, что и учитель, и ученик должны обладать определенными навыками для организации эффективного урока.

Abstract

The article elaborates advantages and disadvantages of online learning in educational process. It has been noted that after the coronavirus pandemic spread, it left its tracks in education system. Some education centers shifted to online education format from a traditional form. The article underlines that online learning is time and cost efficient while it is not observed at traditional face-to-face lessons. It is emphasized that both teachers and student have to possess some skills in order to organize an efficient lesson.

Ключевые слова: онлайн-обучение, образование, эффективное, затратное, преимущество, недостаток.

Keywords: online learning, education, efficient, costly, advantage, disadvantage

Nowadays, online learning is becoming customary and some teachers and students prefer to have the lessons on this platform rather than in a traditional way. Today, coronavirus pandemic has urged us to be accustomed to a new and difficult form of education –online learning. Prior to pandemic, this form of education was specific only for America, Canada and Australia because of long distance between schools and homes. But now it has become a reality for everyone to recognize and accept online learning as a priority. Once the pandemic emerged, most education institutions were not ready for online education because of the lack of some electronic devices and applications. But after a short period of time, man-kind could find the most possible solutions to this challenge. They eliminated technical problems by providing education centers with teaching devices and began to instruct teachers and students on online lessons. Coronavirus pandemic left its unforgettable track in our daily life. Hence, in 2020, the global coronavirus pandemic prompted most universities to hastily shift to online learning in lieu of holding classes in person [1] For example, though IELTS speaking test was only face-to-face previously, now it is a trend to conduct the speaking test via online video call at the test center. It means that the lockdown taught us a new way-out and suggested us more profitable and flexible solutions to this problem which will be scrutinized below.

There are a number of advantages of online learning; first of it is time-consuming. The students save time instead of commuting to school, university or college. They can easily find time to study their lessons in

this time lapse. Besides, the students don't spend way fare to reach the education centers. It means that they don't pay any money for transportation means, The sum they have to spend remains in their pockets. Of course, this is economically advantageous for the students. Another merit of online learning is that the students save money in the process of online learning. Instead of buying paper books, copy-books and pens to fulfill education process, they read e-books from the internet, they don't use pens, pencils, erasers, markers and note-books which may cost a great deal of money. Since they can note down any information delivered by lecturer via keyboard on the computer or laptop.

When the register-book is electronic, the paper which is obtained from the trees is not wasted. Along with books, copy-books, register-books and other documents are not bought and it is considered to be cost-efficient.

Besides, they don't have expenditure in clothes. As we know, there is a uniform in many secondary comprehensive schools and some colleges and universities whose leaderships in those education centers require. This rule is compulsory in those education institutions. The students don't have to buy those uniforms and prefer wearing their own casual clothes. In which they feel more confident and convenient rather than wear boring uniforms and feel depressed under strict compulsory rules of education center. It means that they save up money by sitting at home and by not buying those clothes.

There is one more benefit of online learning in terms of teaching aids or materials. For example, The teaching materials are uploaded in the system called LMS (Learning Management System) and the students may easily enter the system and pick the appropriate lectures without wasting time to look for the relevant topics in uncertain books assigned by the senior lecturer at a traditional lesson.

Online learning environments provide a greater degree of flexibility than traditional classroom setting [2]. Flexibility is the next advantage of online learning. Unlike face-to-face lessons determined during an exact time according to schedule, time can be very flexible both for the teachers and students. After coming to a mutual agreement, the teacher and students set a flexible time for themselves which can be very suitable. The problem of overlapping of other subjects at traditional lessons can be solved by conducting evening lessons online. Furthermore, some students might find a job and work during the day and evening classes are particularly suitable for them.

Online platforms can also offer more diverse representations of student populations as learners prepare for working in the twenty-first century [4].

Along with advantages, online education also has some drawbacks which is enumerated below;

a) the attendance to the online lessons is not so strict as traditional lesson; in online lesson too much confidence and convenience result in irresponsibility of some students. Some students don't participate in the online lessons caviling that there is a poor connection or they don't have internet access or relevant conditions such as laptops, computers, notepads, etc.

b) control over the quality of the students results is very weak; when the teacher asks questions and the students answer them, the teacher is not sure whether the students take advantage of some materials behind the camera or not. The students may use the internet and find the relevant answers to the asked questions very swiftly due to the fast search on the Google. Once they make a search on the questions and find answers to them, they may just read them and the teacher may listen and suppose that the student is fully ready for the lesson. It means that the teacher may be deceived in the process of online education.

c) poor supervision over the students' behaviors. Though most of the students in online learning join the lesson, they may hide and avoid listening to the lesson by closing the camera and dealing with other improper things. These treatments may also be observed in traditional lessons, as well though the percentage is supposed to be higher than backbenchers participating in those lessons.

We had better clarify the concept of improving and maintenance of software such as computers, laptops, notepads, etc. It is undeniable that they are costly and some low income students can't afford buying them. Some universities can provide the students with those technical devices but it is usually available mostly

in the territory of university. The students are not allowed to carry those devices to their houses.

We should confess that the number of technical staff to support, supply, set and repair of technical devices may not be sufficient. Most education institutions are not ready to pay salary for numerous employees dealing with technical issues in order to provide the students and the teachers with lessons of high quality. In case the technical staff is absent, the teacher should be obliged to implement multiple functions;

- the teacher should know how to set the programs like a programmer;

- the teacher should be able to fix the device when it is out of order like a computer engineer. The teachers are obliged to carry out all technical issues themselves.

- the teacher has to take photos and videos to prove that he, really, had an online lesson which education centers demand. In this case, the teacher becomes a skilled cameraman and a photographer.

- the teacher should be an artful designer and able to design lectures with attractive colors in Power Point program.

In this job, not only teachers but also students should be able to master some skills. The students should own the following skills;

- The students must learn computer skills and must be able apply them properly.

- The students must improve their fast writing skills on the keyboard of the computer or laptop which they need to note down a lecture.

- Like teachers, the students also should be a good programmer and a repairer. They should be able to download programs as Zoom, Webex, Microsoft team or Bandicam on their devices.

- the students should be a good designer in order to present the demonstration lesson assigned by the teacher as a task.

- it helps students implement action-oriented solutions [3, p.220].

Consequently, it should be noted that online learning has more privileges than the drawbacks.

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